

Socio-Economic Impacts of COVID-19 on Urban Poor Households in Bahir Dar city, Ethiopia

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Abstract: This study examines the socio-economic impacts of COVID-19 on urban poor households in Bahir Dar city, Ethiopia, focusing on material living conditions, education, economic status, health, and social relations. A descriptive research design was employed, combining quantitative surveys of 349 household participants. Descriptive statistics and mean score analysis assessed changes in living conditions, while thematic analysis captured participants' perspectives. The results reveal that the pandemic significantly disrupted livelihoods: 47% of households reported changes in goods and services, and 65% experienced reduced food consumption, particularly in meal frequency and dietary diversity. Education was negatively affected due to limited digital access and weak family support, resulting in low performance and increased dropout rates. Economically, households faced job losses, income decline, and rising debts, while health outcomes deteriorated due to reduced healthcare access and increased psychological distress. Conversely, social networks strengthened, as families and neighbors shared resources and provided emotional support, acting as informal safety nets.

Overall, the study demonstrates that COVID-19 deepened vulnerabilities among the urban poor, while highlighting the critical role of community support in coping with crises. These findings underscore the need for integrated policies to enhance resilience in health, education, and economic systems for marginalized urban populations.

Keywords: COVID-19, urban poor, material living conditions, education, economic impact, health, social networks

1. Introduction

The outbreak of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) has created unprecedented global health and socio-economic challenges. Declared a public health emergency of international concern by the World Health Organization (WHO) in January 2020, the pandemic quickly spread worldwide, disrupting livelihoods and triggering a global recession (Qiu et al., 2020; Chakraborty & Maity, 2020). For Sub-Saharan African countries, including Ethiopia, the crisis has imposed a considerable burden on fragile economies with limited capacity to respond (OECD, 2020).

Ethiopia confirmed its first case on March 13, 2020 (Mekonnen et al., 2020), followed by nationwide restrictions including school closures, bans on public gatherings, border controls, and

a state of emergency (Kebede et al., 2020). While necessary to curb transmission, these measures disrupted economic activities and disproportionately affected vulnerable groups. Workers in the informal sector, small enterprises, and daily wage laborers faced severe income losses, food insecurity, and reduced access to services (Rakib et al., 2020; Schotte et al., 2021).

In Bahir Dar, the capital of Amhara region, stay-at-home measures and business disruptions significantly affected informal workers and socially disadvantaged households. The city administration estimates that more than 11,000 households—12.1% of the total—are socio-economically vulnerable, with female-headed households constituting the majority (Bahir Dar City Administration Social Affairs Office, 2023). These households typically face limited access to healthcare, education, and stable income, and the pandemic has further weakened their coping mechanisms.

Although several studies in Ethiopia have examined the health, psychological, and macroeconomic consequences of COVID-19 (Abate et al., 2020; Fikiru et al., 2021; Deshpande et al., 2022), limited attention has been given to the urban poor, despite their heightened vulnerability and vital role in urban economies. There is also limited empirical evidence on the integrated socio-economic impacts of the pandemic on urban poor households in Bahir Dar, especially using household-level quantitative data. This study addresses this gap by providing a descriptive quantitative assessment of the socio-economic consequences of COVID-19 on urban poor households in Bahir Dar, Northwestern Ethiopia. Findings from this research are expected to inform policy responses aimed at reducing vulnerability and strengthening resilience among disadvantaged urban populations.

Research objectives

- To identify the influence of COVID-19 on material living conditions of urban poor.
- To assess the consequence of COVID-19 on education of urban poor households.
- To identify the effect of COVID-19 on economic conditions of urban poor households.
- To find out the consequence of COVID-19 on health of urban poor in Bahir Dar city.
- To investigate the impact of COVID-19 on social relations of urban poor households.

2. Literature Review

Urban residents and COVID-19 crisis

The pandemic has hit cities unequally, with sharp differences between countries and even within the same country. Poverty, exclusion, and insecure living conditions significantly increased infection risks, making COVID-19 as much a social crisis as a health one (Friedmann & Bartsch, 2020). In countries like the US, Brazil, the UK, and India, poor and low-income groups have been disproportionately affected (Fisher & Bubola, 2020). Cities with greater inequality suffered the most, as the crisis exposed and deepened existing social divides (Kotsila, 2020).

The poorest not only bore the brunt of infections but also faced harsher consequences from policy responses, including lack of access to housing, healthcare, and healthy food (Simon, 2020). Informal workers, concentrated in low- and middle-income countries, were especially vulnerable—lacking social protection, losing over 60% of their income, and largely excluded from support measures (Lee et al., 2020).

Weak social safety nets worsened the crisis in developing countries, driving up food insecurity and poverty. Globally, an estimated 88–115 million people were pushed into extreme poverty in 2020, with Sub-Saharan Africa most affected (Lese et al., 2021).

Socioeconomic Indicators and COVID-19

Material Living Conditions: - **reflected** in household consumption and housing quality, are key indicators of living standards (Loopstra et al., 2016). COVID-19 disrupted food supply chains and worsened food insecurity, especially among the urban poor (FAO, 2020). Lockdowns reduced access to nutritious foods (Schmidt et al., 2020) and impacted households through health shocks, income loss, and medical expenses (Barrios-Arellano et al., 2022), government restrictions (Abay et al., 2020), and market disruptions (Hirvonen et al., 2020; Mahajan & Tomar, 2020). Other factors such as income declines, demand shocks, hoarding, and policy interventions further constrained food access (Martin & Glauber, 2020). Rising food prices lowered consumption of nutrient-rich foods, with 34% of South Africans reporting hunger during lockdown (Bekker et al., 2020). In Sub-Saharan Africa, reliance on remittances heightened vulnerability; in Ethiopia, falling remittances cut household consumption (Asare et al., 2020).

Economic Conditions: - COVID-19 caused severe economic disruption, with 81% of the global workforce affected by workplace closures (ILO, 2020). Africa, heavily reliant on informal employment and weak social protection, faced sharp GDP declines and rising poverty, with up to 14 million people projected to fall into **extreme poverty** (Cilliers et al., 2020). Income losses were widespread, especially among informal and self-employed workers lacking savings **or safety nets** 88% reported declines in some countries (Ejeromedoghene et al., 2020; Kansime et al., 2021). In Ethiopia's Amhara region, where 31% of urban residents work informally, vulnerability was especially high (Tadele et al., 2020). Business closures, falling sales, and reduced consumption further deepened urban households' economic fragility (De Vito & Gómez, 2020; Hossain, 2021).

Education: - COVID-19 severely disrupted education, with 87% of learners worldwide affected by school closures (UNESCO, 2020). In Ethiopia, schools closed on 16 March 2020, and many students especially from low-income urban households lacked access to online or broadcast-based alternatives (Mengistie, 2020; Tiruneh et al., 2020). Limited technology, parental support, and digital literacy widened pre-existing inequalities between poor and wealthier students (Owusu-Fordjour et al., 2015; Masters et al., 2020). Closures also heightened anxiety and stress, while financial hardship and performance setbacks may prevent some families from sending children back to school (Woday et al., 2020).

Health and Access to Basic Health Facilities: - COVID-19 caused severe global health impacts, with the USA, India, and Brazil recording the highest fatalities. Ethiopia reported over 500,000 cases and 7,500 deaths, including 6,162 cases in Bahir Dar (Johns Hopkins University [JHU], 2021; Amhara Public Health Institute, 2023). Beyond illness and mortality, the pandemic fueled widespread anxiety, depression, and stress (Akbari et al., 2021; WHO, 2022). In Sub-Saharan Africa, weak health systems, reduced service utilization, and resource shortages worsened chronic illness and preventable deaths (Assefa et al., 2021; Roder-DeWan, 2020). Lockdowns disrupted maternal and child health services, potentially adding over a million deaths in low-income countries (WHO, 2020). Urban poor communities, facing overcrowding and poor sanitation, were disproportionately exposed to health risks and inequalities (Auerbach & Thachil, 2020).

Social Relations and Connections: - COVID-19 significantly disrupted social relationships, which normally strengthen during crises. Restrictions on gatherings and mobility reduced face-to-face contact, heightening isolation, loneliness, and anxiety (Gupta et al., 2021; Brook et al., 2020). While digital technologies became crucial for maintaining interaction, poor urban households often lacked internet access, deepening exclusion (Alcendor, 2020). Community and family networks provided essential support through food sharing, lending, and emotional help (Kabir et al., 2023), yet overcrowded living conditions and restrictions strained these bonds. Overall, the pandemic weakened traditional social structures and exposed the vulnerability of the urban poor to isolation during health crises.

Theoretical Framework: Vulnerability Theory

This study applied Vulnerability Theory, which highlights how exposure, sensitivity, and adaptive capacity shape the susceptibility of individuals or households to external shocks such as pandemics (Cutter, Boruff, & Shirley, 2003; Adger, 2006). In the case of COVID-19, urban poor households in Bahir Dar were particularly vulnerable due to low income, insecure livelihoods, inadequate housing, and limited access to health and education services, all of which heightened their risks while constraining coping mechanisms and social protection.

3. Method and materials

This study adopted a descriptive quantitative research design to examine the socio-economic impacts of COVID-19 on urban poor households in Bahir Dar city, Northwestern Ethiopia. A cross-sectional household survey was implemented to collect numerical data appropriate for statistical analysis. The research was carried out in Bahir Dar city, the capital of the Amhara National Regional State and one of Ethiopia's major urban centers, where residents are engaged in both formal and informal economic activities. According to the city administration (2023), around 11,368 households (12.1%) fall under the category of socially vulnerable, making Bahir Dar city a relevant context for exploring the pandemic's effects on disadvantaged urban groups. A total sample of 386 households was determined using Yamane's (1967) formula with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. To ensure adequate representation across sub-cities, stratified random sampling was applied, followed by proportional selection of households within each stratum using systematic random sampling. Data collection was carried out through a structured questionnaire administered over a three-week period in 2024.

4. Results

4.1. Demographic Profiles of Respondents

The demographic profiles of the participants include their gender, age, marital status and their educational level. Moreover, their occupation, monthly income and their family members were identified and illustrated as follows;

Table 1 Demographic Profile of Respondents

No		Frequency	Percent (%)
1	Gender of the respondents		
	Male	118	33.8
	Female	231	66.2
	Total	349	100.0
2	Age of the respondents		
	18-25	12	3.4
	26-35	242	69.3
	36-45	70	20.1

	46-55	23	6.6
	>56	2	.6
	Total	349	100.0
3	Marital status of respondents		
	Married	70	20.1
	Non married	77	22.1
	Divorced	171	49.0
	widowed	31	8.9
	Total	349	100.0
4	Educational levels of the respondents		
	Primary education	96	27.5
	Secondary education	143	41.0
	College Diploma	72	20.6
	university/ Bachelor	14	4.0
	Non-educated	24	6.9
	Total	349	100.0

Source; survey result (2024)

The study involved 349 participants, of whom most were females (66.2%), showing that female-headed poor households are more common in Bahir Dar city. Regarding marital status, nearly half (49%) were divorced, while 22.1% were non-married, 20.1% married, and 8.9% widowed, indicating that most household heads live without a spouse. Age-wise, the majority was youths; with 69.3% aged 26–35 and 20.1% aged 36–45. In terms of education, most had secondary (41%) or primary (27.5%) education, while fewer held college diplomas (20.6%), and very few were degree holders (4%) or non-educated (6.9%).

Table 2 Occupation and income of the respondents

No		Frequency	Percent (%)
1	Occupation of the respondents		
	Construction workers	80	22.9
	rickshaw pullers	53	15.2
	day laborers	64	18.3
	street vendor	112	32.1
	other	40	11.5
	Total	349	100.0
2	Monthly Income of the respondents in (Eth. Birr)		
	< 1000	0	0
	1001-2000	8	2.3
	2001-3000	217	62.2
	3001- 4000	120	34.4
	4001-5000	4	1.1
	>5000	0	0
	Total	349	100.0
3	Family members of the participants		
	1	33	9.5
	2	175	50.1
	3	115	33.0
	4	21	6.0
	5	5	1.4
	Total	349	100.0

Source; survey result (2024)

Most respondents were street vendors (32.1%), followed by petty traders (22.9%), construction workers (18.3%), day laborers (15.2%), and others (11.5%). These occupations were highly vulnerable to disruption during lockdowns. In terms of income, the majority (62.2%) earned 2001–3000 ETB per month, while very few earned above 3000 ETB, reflecting the extremely low earnings that made it difficult to afford pandemic protection measures. Regarding family size, half (50.1%) of the households had only two members, followed by three members (33%), while larger families were rare. This indicates that most urban poor households in Bahir Dar are small in size, largely because the heads are relatively young.

4.2. Consequence of COVID-19 on Material living condition

The outbreak of the pandemic has created strong impact on urban poor at household level in terms of goods and services they have in their house and their consumption pattern.

In this part the consequence of the pandemic on material living condition of urban poor is manipulated and presented as a finding of the study. The study result is compiled by including the descriptive data, the qualitative responses of the participants and the quantitative statistical results.

Table 3 COVID-19 and material living condition

		Frequency	Percent
Is there any change in goods and services of your house after the outbreak of the pandemic?	Yes	164	47.0
	No	185	53.0
	Total	349	100.0
Does COVID-19 have affected your food consumption pattern?	yes	227	65.0
	No	122	35.0
	Total	349	100.0

Source; survey result (2024)

Among the participants of this study, 164 (47.0%) of them revealed that COVID-19 outbreak have an impact on their housing goods and services and the rest 185 (53.0%) responded, their housing goods and services are not changed due to the outbreak and controlling measures of COVID19. This result indicates the outbreak of the pandemic have forced urban poor to change goods and service they use in their house.

According to 227 (65.0%) (See table 3 above) respondents COVID-19 pandemic and its measures have affected their food consumption pattern while 122 (35.0%) revealed that the pandemic did not affect their consumption pattern in a household level. Based on this result, the pandemic have affected those urban poor in terms of their consumption pattern and their eating habit.

Table 4 Material living condition Scale Items

Items of the Variable	N	Mean	Std. deviation
I sold housing materials to cover living cost after the pandemic	349	2.88	1.324
I sold housing materials to recover from debt due to the pandemic	349	3.73	.879
I tried to settle hand washing facilities to practice good hygiene in my house after the pandemic	349	3.82	.775
Air ventilation and other facilities like windows are prepared to keep the house air condition fresh after the pandemic	349	3.73	.793
The family eat less in amount due to economic constraints after the pandemic	349	3.79	.781

The family eat less in frequency per day since the outbreak of the pandemic	349	3.91	.851
The family Consumed less meat, fish and fruits after the outbreak of the pandemic	349	3.92	.787
Material living condition		3.68	.423

Source; survey result (2024)

According to the respondents, their material living condition has been changed with mean score of **(3.68)** and std. deviation of (0.423). The Pandemic have the greatest impact on the family Consumption of meat, fish and fruits after the outbreak of the pandemic with the mean score of (3.92) and followed by the family eat less in frequency per day since the outbreak of the pandemic and the household has tried to settle hand washing facilities to practice good hygiene in their house after the pandemic with the mean score of (3.91) and (3.82) respectively (**See table 4 above**).

4.3. Consequence of COVID-19 on Education

Education indicates the attendance of family members at school from KG to secondary education levels and their academic performance. The outbreak of COVID-19 has a consequence on urban poor household members who was attending school. The study result regarding consequence of the pandemic on education is revealed using the qualitative responses of the participants.

Table 5 COVID-19 and Education

		Frequency	Percent
Is there any family member who is learning in schools in the pandemic era?	Yes	229	65.6
	No	120	34.4
	Total	349	100.0
Do you think that COVID-19 have affected students' performance?	yes	238	68.2
	No	111	31.8
	Total	349	100.0

Source; survey result (2024)

Participants were asked about if there is a student in their family and 229 (65.6%) of them has a student in their family with different educational level. And the rest 120 (34.4%) participants reveal there is no student in their family member. Among the respondents (**See table 4.5 above**) 238 (68.2%) believes the outbreak of the pandemic has affected the performance of students and the remaining 111(31.8%) don't think that the pandemic has affected students' performance.

Table 6 Education Scale Items

Items of the Variable	N	Mean	Std. deviation
Children attending school has been ceased after the outbreak	349	3.36	1.018
The performance of the students has been decreased since the pandemic	349	3.60	.925
Children attitude towards their learning has been changed in negative way since the outbreak of the pandemic	349	3.75	.746
During schools closure the level of anxiety, depression disorders, and stress are high among students	349	3.85	.756
Children have not accessed to radios, television and the internet lessons during the lockdowns	349	3.79	.808
Families were not conscious to support children to engage with digital educational activities during the lock down	349	3.87	.832
Education		3.7030	.50662

Source; survey result (2024)

The mean score of education is **(3.70)** and standard deviation of **(0.507)** which shows that respondents have awareness about the effect of the pandemic on Education.

Among items measuring the effect of COVID-19 on education, families were not conscious to support students to engage with digital educational activities during the lock down scores the highest mean with (3.87) and followed by during schools closure the level of anxiety, depression disorders, and stress was high among students and students have not accessed to radios, television and the internet lessons during the lockdowns with the mean score of **(3.85)** and **(3.79)** respectively (See **table 6 above**). This finding indicates the pandemic has a consequence on educational performance and attendance of urban poor family members due to lack of family support in using digital learning that was implemented during the pandemic era and by creating stress among students.

4.4. Consequence of COVID-19 on Economic condition

Economic condition refers income, saving, employment condition and debt of a household during the pandemic era. COVID-19 has a consequence on Economic condition of urban poor households. As per the house head participants, the result of the study about the consequence of the pandemic on economic condition is illustrated using the descriptive data, the qualitative responses of the participants' results as follows.

Table 7 COVID-19 and Economic condition

		Frequency	Percent
Did the pandemic affect your employment situation?	Yes	151	43.3
	No	198	56.7
	Total	349	100.0
Is there any change on your occupation due to the outbreak of the pandemic?	yes	114	32.7
	No	235	67.3
	Total	349	100.0
Does COVID-19 outbreak have an impact on your income?	Yes	311	89.1
	No	38	10.9
	Total	349	100.0

Source; survey result (2024)

Respondents were asked about the effect of the outbreak of the pandemic, majority of them 198 (56.7%) proved that there is no an effect on their employment situation and the remaining 151(43.3%) of the participants claimed the outbreak of the pandemic affects their employment situation. This result indicates as most urban poor engaged with informal sectors, their occupation status was not significantly affected. Among the participants who believe the pandemic has effect on their employment situation 114 (75%) of them have changed their occupation due to the outbreak of the pandemic.

Among the participants of this study, (See **table 7 above**) majority of them 311 (89.1%) revealed that COVID-19 outbreak have an impact on their income and the rest 38 (10.9%) responded that their income is not affected by the outbreak and controlling measures of COVID19. This result indicates, the outbreak of the pandemic has serious impact on the income of urban poor in Bahir Dar city.

Table 8 Level of the decrease of income

	Frequency	Percent
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If you think that your income is decreased after the pandemic please select the situation?	Decreased by about half of the usual	150	43.0
	Decreased by more than half of the usual	139	39.8
	Decreased by less than half of the usual	38	10.9
	other	22	6.3
	Total	349	100.0

Source; survey result (2024)

Respondents were asked if they thought that their income is decreased due to the pandemic and to select the situation based on described alternatives. Most of the participants 150 (43.0%) proved that their income is decreased by about half of their usual monthly income. 139 (39.8%) of them illustrate their monthly income is decreased by more than half of the usual and followed by 38 (10.9%) who said their income is decreased by less than half of the usual due to the pandemic and its measures (See table 8 above). This result indicates that the outbreak of the pandemic forced urban poor to lose nearly half of their average income prior to the pandemic.

Table 9 Economic condition Scale Items

Items of the Variable	N	Mean	Std. deviation
My income has been decreased since the outbreak of the pandemic	349	3.49	.886
My saving amount has been decreased after the outbreak of the pandemic	349	3.55	.865
I feel precariousness about my employment status during the pandemic	349	3.80	.714
My debt of has been increased due to the pandemic	349	3.90	.734
The house hold buying power has been decreased after the pandemic	349	3.92	.715
I face a job loss problem in the pandemic era	349	3.80	.790
Economic condition		3.74	.425

Source; survey result (2024)

Based on the study result, the house hold buying power has been decreased after the pandemic scores the highest mean score (3.92) with standard deviation of (0.425) followed by the debt of a household has been increased due to the pandemic and feel of precariousness about their employment status during the pandemic era mean score (3.90) and (3.80) respectively (See Table 9 above).

4.5. Consequence of COVID-19 on Health

Health refers a threat of infection and access to care facilities among the household family members during the pandemic era. As per the household head participants of the study COVID-19 and implementation of its measures has a consequence on health of urban poor households. The finding is interpreted using the descriptive data, the qualitative responses and the quantitative statistical results as follows.

Table 10 COVID-19 and Health

		Frequency	Percent
Did you have ever been contracted with COVID-19?	Yes	46	13.2
	No	303	86.8
	Total	349	100.0
Did the pandemic era influence your psychological and emotional feeling?	yes	313	89.7
	No	36	10.3
	Total	349	100.0

Do you have sufficient access to medical treatment?	yes	73	20.9
	No	276	79.1
	Total	349	100.0

Source; survey result (2024)

Among the participants of the study 46 (13.2%) of them have noticed that they have contracted with COVID-19. And majority of them 303 (86.8%) have never been contracted with COVID-19. Based on this finding, most urban poor households in Bahir Dar city are not contracted with COVID-19 pandemic. Participants were also asked about the effect of the pandemic on their psychological and emotional feeling which are the dimensions of mental health and majority of them 313 (89.7%) have been affected by the pandemic. And the rest 36 (10.3%) of the participants reveal the pandemic did not create influence on their regular psychological and emotional feeling. During the pandemic era most respondents 276 (79.1%) did not get sufficient access to medical treatment due to different reasons. Based on this result, the health access of urban poor was highly affected by the outbreak of the pandemic.

Participants of the study were asked to reason out why they did not get sufficient access to medical treatment and most of them 214 (61.3%) are not accessed health services due to Lack of money. And 110 (31.5%) of them are not admitting health institutions due to the fear of the contract of COVID-19 at treatment areas (See table 11 below).

Table 11 Medical treatment access of respondents

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Lack of money	215	61.6
	Hospital/clinic not having enough supply	7	2.0
	Lack/Limitation on transportation	9	2.6
	Turned away because facility was closed	6	1.7
	No medical personnel available	3	.9
	fear of COVID-19 in health institutions	109	31.2
	Total	349	100.0

Source: survey result (2024)

The rest small portions of participants reveal they are not getting access to medical treatment due to lack/limitation on transportation in stay at home era 9 (2.6%), hospital/clinic not having enough supply 7 (2.0%) and no medical personnel available 3 (0.9%) (See table 11 above). This finding indicates urban poor are not visiting health institution due to financial problems and fear of the contract of COVID-19 at health institutions.

Table 12 Health Scale Items

Items of the Variable Variables	N	Mean	Std.deviation
we feel fear and distress in the pandemic era	349	3.58	1.103
A family member had contracted COVID-19 in major or symptom level	349	3.50	.999
we lack health access during the pandemic era as household level	349	3.57	.899
Household member needed medical treatment after outbreak but unable to access due to economic constraint	349	3.60	.887
Health providers performed less and facilities often lacked necessary equipment and supplies in the pandemic era.	349	3.74	.927
We fear being contracted to the virus while go to health facilities and avoid seeking care behavior during the pandemic era	349	3.77	.952

Health	349	3.64	.567
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Source; survey result (2024)

Based on the descriptive result, respondents fear for being contracted to the virus while go to health facilities and avoid seeking care behavior during the pandemic era contributes the most with the mean score of (3.77) (See table 12 above) followed by health providers performed less and facilities often lacked necessary equipment and supplies in the pandemic era and household member needed medical treatment after the outbreak of the pandemic but unable to access due to economic constraint with mean score of (3.74) and (3.60) respectively.

4.6. Consequence of COVID-19 on Social relations

Social relation is the interaction among parents, between friends and other people, governmental and non-governmental institutions. The outbreak of COVID-19 has created a consequence on social relation and connection of urban poor households. The result of the study about the consequence of the pandemic on social relation of urban poor is presented using the descriptive data, the qualitative responses of the participants and the quantitative statistical results as follows.

Table 13 COVID-19 and Social relations

		Frequency	Percent
Did COVID-19 affect your relationship with your neighbors?	yes	259	74.2
	No	90	25.8
	Total	349	100.0
Did COVID-19 affect your relationship with your family members?	yes	178	51.0
	No	171	49.0
	Total	349	100.0

Source; survey result (2024)

Respondents were asked about the effect of the pandemic in their social relationship and 259 (74.2 %) of the respondents agreed that COVID-19 affected their relationship with neighbors. The remaining 90 (25.8%) of the participants revealed the outbreak of the pandemic did not affect their relationship with their neighbors. 178 (51.0%) explained that COVID-19 affect their relationship with their family members and nearly half of the respondents 171(49.0%) point out that the outbreak of COVID-19 did not affect relationship they have with their family members (See table 13 above). This result indicates the outbreak of the pandemic affected the social connection of urban poor that makes them more connected with their families, neighbors or friends.

Table 14 Social relations Scale Items

Variables	N	Mean	Std. deviation
Interaction between family members has been increased during the pandemic	349	3.74	.588
Interaction between friends has been increased and created strong trusting relationships with each other after the pandemic	349	3.68	.973
Government and institutional relation were created and help to sustain our families.	349	3.59	.907
non-governmental institutions and other people increased their support after the pandemic	349	3.72	.855
Our support each other among neighbors has increased to share food	349	3.85	.803

and borrow money after the pandemic			
The pandemic deepen social ties that help us to navigate stress, hardship, and uncertainty since its outbreak	349	3.89	.847
We were being able to share fears and worries with family in the house hold during the pandemic	349	3.87	.907
Social relations	349	3.765	.4998

Source; survey result (2024)

According to the descriptive data of items measuring social relations, the pandemic deepen social ties that help them to navigate stress, hardship, and uncertainty since its outbreak contribute the most with the mean score of 3.89) and standard deviation of (0.847). respondents were being able to share fears and worries with family in the house hold during the pandemic and their support each other among neighbors has increased to share food and borrow money after the pandemic contributes significantly to the consequence of the pandemic on their social relation with the mean score of (3.87) and (3.85) respectively. Government and institutional relation that were created to help to sustain their families contribute less with mean score of (3.59) (See **Table 14**).

5. Discussion

This study shows that COVID-19 has considerably affected the material living conditions of urban poor households in Bahir Dar. Almost half of the respondents (47%) reported changes in household goods and services, while two-thirds (65%) indicated that their food consumption patterns were negatively affected. This highlights the pandemic's strong impact on basic living standards, particularly food security. Similar findings are reported globally, where low-income households faced rising food insecurity and asset depletion due to income loss and rising costs (FAO, 2020; Sumner, Hoy, & Ortiz-Juarez, 2020). The mean score for material living conditions (M = 3.68) confirms moderate deterioration, with the greatest effects seen in reduced consumption of meat, fish, and fruits (M = 3.92) and lower meal frequency (M = 3.91). These coping strategies mirror trends observed in other developing contexts, where vulnerable groups sacrificed dietary diversity during crises (Headey et al., 2020; Hirvonen, de Brauw, & Abate, 2021). On a positive note, households also reported adopting preventive measures such as installing hand washing facilities (M = 3.82) and improving ventilation (M = 3.73), reflecting health awareness despite economic constraints (Naser et al., 2020). Overall, the findings confirm that the pandemic deepened vulnerabilities of the poor by eroding food security and assets, consistent with vulnerability theory, which emphasizes that shocks disproportionately affect groups with limited resilience (Cutter, Boruff, & Shirley, 2003; Adger, 2006).

The findings reveal that COVID-19 severely disrupted education among urban poor households due to limited digital materials, lack of family support, and weak capacity to adapt to new learning modalities. These challenges led to poor academic performance, negative attitudes toward learning, and increased dropout rates. Studies confirm that school closures heightened anxiety, stress, and depression among students, which negatively affected learning outcomes (Woday et al., 2020; Tiruneh, 2020). Moreover, socio-economic and cultural inequalities limited access to learning opportunities (Bonal & González, 2020), while inadequate facilities, poor digital skills, and resistance to new methods further constrained education systems (Adedoyin & Soykan, 2020). Lack of internet connectivity widened the gap between students who could and could not access online learning, particularly disadvantaging children from digitally illiterate and low-income families (Masters et al., 2020; Mengistie, 2020). Overall, the pandemic exacerbated educational inequalities, contributed to dropouts, and weakened families' ability to finance

schooling, leaving urban poor students highly vulnerable (Azorín, 2020; Pokhrel & Chhetri, 2021).

The findings indicate that COVID-19 severely affected the economic condition of urban poor households in Bahir Dar, reflected in declining purchasing power, job loss, income reduction, and rising debt. Similar patterns were observed across Africa, where lockdowns triggered widespread income shocks—44% in Uganda and Kenya (Kansiime et al., 2021) and income drops for nearly half of households in Kenya, Mozambique, Nigeria, South Africa, and Côte d'Ivoire (Ejeromedoghene et al., 2020; Sers & Mughal, 2020). The pandemic's economic burden fell disproportionately on informal workers, who often lacked contracts, savings, and job security (Barnett-Howell et al., 2021; Douglas et al., 2020). In Ethiopia, where most workers are employed in the informal sector, recovery is likely to remain slow (Tadele et al., 2020). Many poor households also fell into cycles of debt and borrowing that persist beyond the crisis (Kamal & Islam, 2022). Overall, the pandemic deepened the economic vulnerability of the urban poor, trapping many in unstable livelihoods and long-term financial hardship.

Based on this result, fear of the contract of COVID-19 at health institutions decreased the seeking care behavior or urban poor during the pandemic era.

The findings show that COVID-19 had serious health consequences for urban poor households in Bahir Dar. Nationally, over 501,000 cases and 7,574 deaths were reported, with Bahir Dar recording 6,162 cases and 157 deaths (Amhara Public Health Institute, 2023). Beyond infection, the pandemic caused widespread psychological distress—stress, anxiety, and depression—exacerbated by high mortality, lack of vaccines, and difficult living conditions (Akbari et al., 2021; Bendau et al., 2021; WHO, 2022). Prolonged anxiety disrupted daily life and weakened mental well-being (Raesi et al., 2020; Bao et al., 2020).

The crisis also reduced utilization of essential health services, increasing risks of chronic illness and preventable mortality (Assefa et al., 2021). Weak health system capacity, shortages of supplies, and poor preparedness further disrupted both preventive and curative care (Papautsky et al., 2020; Roder-DeWan, 2020). Fear of infection discouraged care-seeking, and in some cases, patients received inappropriate treatment (Orthop, 2020; Sorenson et al., 2020). Vulnerable groups, especially slum residents, faced heightened risks due to overcrowding, poor housing, and limited access to clean water and sanitation (Auerbach & Thachil, 2020).

The findings suggest that COVID-19 strengthened social connections among urban poor households, providing critical support during times of stress and hardship. Families and neighbors shared food, lent money, and offered emotional support, acting as informal safety nets that helped households cope with income loss and escalating debts (Kabir et al., 2023). During lockdowns, family members spent more time together, improving relationships, while neighborly interactions also increased, fostering mutual aid and trust. In densely populated areas, neighbors often became like extended family, prioritizing collective survival over individual needs. Overall, the pandemic reinforced community bonds, enabling urban poor households to navigate economic, social, and emotional challenges in Bahir Dar.

Conclusion

This study examined the impacts of COVID-19 on the socio-economic conditions of urban poor households in Bahir Dar. The findings show that the pandemic significantly undermined material living conditions, disrupted education, weakened economic stability, and reduced access to health services, while at the same time strengthening social ties as coping mechanisms.

Households reported selling assets, reducing meal frequency, and cutting back on nutritious foods, confirming that food insecurity was a major consequence of the pandemic. Education inequalities widened due to lack of digital access and family support, leading to poor performance and dropouts. Economically, urban poor households were severely affected by job loss, income decline, and debt accumulation, reflecting their reliance on informal employment. Health outcomes deteriorated as fear of infection reduced care-seeking behavior and contributed to mental health problems. On the other hand, social networks provided crucial support, as families and neighbors shared resources and emotional assistance to withstand hardship.

Overall, the pandemic deepened existing vulnerabilities of the urban poor and highlighted systemic weaknesses in food security, education, employment, and health systems. These findings call for targeted policy interventions that strengthen social protection, expand digital and educational access, support informal workers, and improve healthcare preparedness to build resilience against future crises.

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